

PROBLEMS OF STUDYING TECHNICAL VOCABULARY IN NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *Problems of learning of technical words in non-linguistic universities, are raised in this article. According to the author, learning foreign language terminology, particularly technical words, also presents significant challenges. As the author considers, the teacher's task is to teach students the most effective techniques for memorizing new vocabulary, maximizing the use of all memory types. The author highlights the key problems in this area.*

Key words: *aspect, communication, didactic, expand, language, lexical, text, semantic, skill, vocabulary.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada tilshunos bo'lmagan universitetlarda texnik so'zlarni o'rganish muammolari ko'tarilgan. Muallifning fikriga ko'ra, xorijiy til terminologiyasini, xususan, texnik so'zlarni o'rganish ham jiddiy qiyinchiliklarni keltirib chiqaradi. Muallifning fikricha, o'qituvchining vazifasi talabalarga yangi so'z boyligini yodlashning eng samarali usullarini o'rgatish, barcha xotira turlaridan maksimal darajada foydalanishdir. Muallif bu sohadagi asosiy muammolarni ta'kidlaydi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *aspekt, muloqot, didaktik, kengaytirish, til, leksik, matn, semantik, ko'nikma, lug'at.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье поднимаются проблемы изучения технической терминологии в нелингвистических вузах. По мнению автора, изучение терминологии иностранного языка, особенно технической терминологии, также представляет собой значительные трудности. Как считает автор, задача преподавателя состоит в том, чтобы научить студентов наиболее эффективным методам запоминания новой лексики, максимально используя все типы памяти. Автор выделяет ключевые проблемы в этой области.*

Ключевые слова: *аспект, коммуникация, дидактический, расширение, язык, лексический, текст, семантический, навык, лексика.*

When Uzbekistan became an independent state in 1991, the country began carrying out wide-ranging reforms in almost every area of life. Among these, education—especially the teaching of foreign languages—quickly turned into one of the government’s top priorities. The ability to communicate in foreign languages was seen as a crucial tool for global cooperation and competitiveness in the modern world. “Before independence, foreign languages were mainly taught through grammar and translation exercises, with very little focus on real communication. Starting from the 1990s, however, this situation began to change. The government introduced new educational standards, revised curricula, and opened specialized schools and universities aimed at improving language proficiency” [1].

Under President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, “Uzbekistan has transformed foreign language education, establishing a new system to ensure fluency in at least two languages for students, aimed at national competitiveness and international integration. The reform emphasizes

modernizing teaching methods from traditional translation to communicative, technology-driven approaches” [2].

The lexical aspect of foreign language learning is one of the most challenging aspects of foreign language teaching in a technical university. “A limited vocabulary makes students feel insecure and often even reluctant to speak a foreign language, so expanding the vocabulary of students at technical universities is one of the main tasks of foreign language teaching. It is well known that well-developed lexical skills are the main prerequisite for successful communication in a foreign language, while violations of lexical and semantic norms lead to various semantic errors, making speech communicatively imperfect or even completely incomprehensible” [3]. When introducing vocabulary, a differentiated approach to teaching is essential. The methodology for developing vocabulary skills is based on general didactic principles (visibility, accessibility and achievability, consciousness and activity, consistency and systematicity, connection between theory and practice, robustness, and scientific approach) and specific principles related to the specific features of the lexical phenomena being studied. In most technical universities, and general scientific vocabulary is studied in the first year, and specialized and business vocabulary is studied in the second year. “Active vocabulary is included in all areas, but everyday, technical, and general scientific vocabulary requires particular attention. Passive vocabulary primarily includes specialized vocabulary” [4]. Textbooks for non-linguistic universities typically distinguish the following forms of lexical organization of educational material:

- pre-text vocabulary exercises; - text (monologue or dialogue in the form of articles and interviews from magazines and newspapers, general scientific texts, and excerpts from specialized literature); - post-text vocabulary exercises. There are various methods for teaching vocabulary:

1) The grammar-translation method, in which words are memorized before reading the text.

2) The text-translation method, in which words are memorized in the context of authentic texts.

3) Direct methods, in which lexical units are learned in thematic blocks without translation, using visual aids, synonyms and antonyms, and linguistic guesswork.

4) The conscious-comparative method, in which words are memorized both in and out of context, using word-formation features, linguistic guesswork, and translation.

Like any other skill, lexical skills are developed in stages (familiarization, training, practice). Stage I involves the initial introduction of vocabulary. “The purpose of the exercises at this stage of learning is to familiarize students with the sound and graphic representation of a term and its semantic features. Technical terms are another aspect that complicates working with vocabulary in a non-linguistic university” [4]. Since the goal of teaching foreign languages at technical universities is to achieve a level sufficient for practical use of a foreign language in future professional activities, special attention should be paid to the teaching of terminology. In today's environment, a modern engineer cannot succeed in the labor market without a sufficient grasp of terminology, i.e., a sufficiently broad knowledge base for successful professional communication in a foreign language. “For example, 90% of employers note that specialists with foreign language skills working at their company must, above all, be able to communicate using specialized technical terminology. 75% of employers believe that the ability to compile and translate technical documentation describing the operation and maintenance of various devices plays a key role.” [6]. We share the view of many methodologists that learning terminology is

not only a path to successful international cooperation but also a means to a more in-depth understanding of the specialty. However, learning foreign language terminology also presents significant challenges. Firstly, there are no modern foreign-language textbooks or terminology dictionaries for each technical discipline. Secondly, there are no developed methodological foundations for introducing students to terminology relevant to their specialty. Therefore, the first line of work in teaching specialized vocabulary involves the specialized selection of lexical material, including professional vocabulary and terminology. This, on the one hand, develops the professional competencies of future specialists and, on the other, contributes to the formation of their professional motivation.” Working with students at non-linguistic universities, I have come to the conclusion that for the acquisition of vocabulary, especially technical terms, it is crucial to actively engage all types of memory: visual, which develops through reading and writing words; auditory, which is trained by perceiving foreign speech by ear; motor, associated with the functioning of the speech apparatus and the act of recording words in writing; and, ultimately, logical, which enables a full understanding of the material studied” [7]. Therefore, the teacher's task is to teach students the most effective techniques for memorizing new vocabulary, maximizing the use of all memory types.

Students with a predominantly visual memory find it easier to memorize words from flashcards, work with a dictionary, or read text, as if photographing the spelling, translation, and transcription of the word. If auditory memory is dominant, it is more effective to work with audio materials, watch films, or practice with a voice recorder. Many students need some kind of action to memorize new information. They can be advised to write down the word, its translation, and transcription, often multiple times. If visual memory and a rich imagination are well developed, students can be encouraged to memorize new information through images. For example, students can be encouraged to imagine the spelling of the word, the object or action it denotes, its translation, images, and entire situations associated with it. Thus, many experts suggest using the method of mnemonic associations when learning new foreign words. The method consists of finding a phonetic association in Uzbek for the foreign word to be memorized. Then, using imagination and creativity, students must come up with a funny story, rhyme, or phrase with the correct association and a proper translation. All that remains is for the students to memorize the story. Learning technical vocabulary presents a significant challenge for both students and teachers due to the highly specific nature of the terms and the need for a deep understanding of the subject area. The main difficulties stem from the sheer volume of material, the complexity of word structure, and the fact that many common words completely change their meaning in a technical context. Overall, specific problems in learning technical vocabulary include:

1. High density and quantity: Students must learn a large volume of specialized words in short periods, making retention difficult.
2. Abstract concepts: Technical terms often represent complex, theoretical, or symbolic concepts (e.g., in physics) rather than concrete objects, making them harder to grasp.
3. Multiple Meanings (Polysemy): Many technical words have different meanings in general English vs. specialized contexts, leading to confusion.
4. Poor retention and usage: learners struggle to move technical vocabulary from passive recognition to active, correct, and professional production.
5. Pronunciation and **spelling**: Learners often find technical terms difficult to pronounce correctly and spell due to their length or foreign origins.

6. **Limited access to resources:** A lack of specialized, authentic, or engaging materials limits exposure to technical vocabulary in context.

The importance of vocabulary learning for foreign language acquisition cannot be overestimated. A robust vocabulary improves all areas of communication – listening, speaking, writing and reading. A limited vocabulary, on the other hand, impedes successful communication in the classroom and, later, in the workplace. Learning English technical vocabulary poses a lot of difficulties to Romanian engineering students, its open-endedness and lack of rules being seen as the main sources of problems. ESP teachers are also faced with a lot of challenges when teaching technical vocabulary, the decision as to which words to teach, how many words to teach and how to teach them being the most problematic one.

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